

Khafre's pyramid elegantly encodes the speed of light

A fine structure constant.

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Version 1.1.0

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10982350>

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Please check via DOI for latest version.

25 April 2024

Abstract

Alternative Giza researchers are usually aware of at least one of the ways in which the Great Pyramid references the speed of light. Khafre's pyramid also provides the speed of light very elegantly, with a simple exponential formula of base and height.

Keywords: History of Mathematics, History of Science, speed of light, Mathematical Architecture.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Version history

- 1.0.0 21 April 2024 Initial version
- 1.1.0 25 April 2024 Removed necessity for having 3 in formula. Minor edits and polish.

1.2 Symbols and values

I use "cubit" for the Royal cubit (C). Other researchers may use different values, but 0.5236 metres works consistently well for me. It appears that the builders generally worked to four decimal places.

Equations shown below sometimes use a science or engineering approach, not pure mathematics, so $1.999 = 2.0$. We are, after all, using architecture with integer dimensions to approximate various constants.

1.3 The usual apology

Readers of my previous papers will be aware that my explorations at Giza have been “guided.” In recent times “they,” or at least “she,” gradually revealed herself. It was difficult to accept, given who she was, and the crucial parts that she suggests are missing from the history books.

She insisted that Khafre's pyramid also references the speed of light, just like Khufu's (see §2.4). Since I have spent years doing sums with the pyramid dimensions, and had never seen anything remotely like that, I disagreed with her. She insisted. Over and over. So I took another look, got nowhere, begged for clues, and eventually got what I needed to find it, as presented here. So once again, she was right, I was wrong, and I had to apologise and eat humble pie, again.

I realise admissions like this may lead the reader to doubt my sanity. I am shown things, there is no point in denying it, and credit should be given where credit is due. I do not wish to pretend I did it alone. As best as I can figure, this must be some sort of genetic memory, via a process we do not understand. The usual alternative explanations — angels, demons, or aliens — do not appeal to me. Otherwise my subconscious is way better at mathematics than I am.

1.4 When was Khafre built?

The current general consensus is that Khafre reigned from about 2558 BCE. Wikipedia [1], citing Thomas Schneider (*Lexikon der Pharaonen*), settles on “circa 2570 BC,” while stating “Some authors say it was between 2558 BC and 2532 BC,” and uses the 2558 date on the Khafre Pyramid page ([2]), citing Jaromir Malek.

Encyclopædia Britannica [3] says 2575 BCE.

Kate Spence took an astronomical approach (*Ancient Egyptian chronology and the astronomical orientation of pyramids*, [4]), and proposed a date of 2447 BCE. Rawlins and Pickering reviewed her work (*Ancient chronology: Astronomical orientation of the pyramids* [5]) and instead suggested 2607 BCE.

Alexander Puchkov (*Sothic dating of the Egyptian Old Kingdom* [6]) suggests a date of 2810 BCE for Khufu, and that both the Khufu and Khafre pyramids were started at that time in a double project (personal communication).

The website Pharaoh.se [7] additionally lists 2437 (Dodson), 2512 (Arnold), 2520 (Allen), 2547 (v. Beck-erath), and 2576 (Redford), all dates BCE.

If we go back to the experts of 150 years ago, we will find many disparate dates. James Bonwick (*Pyramid facts and fancies* (republished as *The Great Pyramids of Giza: History and Speculation*), 1877 [8]) conveniently catalogued dates for the Great Pyramid for us, Khafre would be a few years later. Examples, all BCE, include Volney 860, Piazzzi Smyth 2170, Wilkinson 2200 to 2500, Nolan 2123 to 2171, Osburn 2300, Fergusson 2600 to 3900, Zincke circa 3000 to 4000, Bunsen 3892, Mariette Bey 3951 to 4235, Lesueur 4000 to 5400, “experts agree” about 6000 years ago, Prof. Owen 4232, and finally, Dufeu 4833 to 4923.

My own research, when it first started to dawn on me that I was being guided, led to a correlation with the Big Dipper star map (*Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [9], see Figure 1 below), which suggests that Giza was built around 55.5k BCE. I do not like that date, but that is when everything works. I was steered there kicking and screaming, and it took a while for me to accept. It is also the only star map that I know of which includes the 4th pyramid reported by Danish explorer Federick Norden (Wikipedia [10], see *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* and also the original papers that were my early steps, *Diskferfery and the Alignment of the Four Main Giza Pyramids* [11] and *55,550 BCE and the 23 Stars of Giza* [12].) The source diagrams are only in Norden's original French version, not the later English translation. He does discuss it in the English version.

Figure 1: Giza double-square site map with star map, 55.5k BCE

The relevance of the date is discussed in §2.3.

2 Mathematics and science

2.1 Decimal vs. fractional notation

The dynastic Egyptians used fractional notation for values less than 1. This was always in the form of unit fractions, i.e. $\frac{1}{integer}$, except for $\frac{2}{3}$.

However, it is clear to me that whoever built Giza used decimal notation, just as we do. The proof for that can be found in the Great Pyramid's King's Chamber (KC), as discussed in *The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game* [13] and *The King's Chamber Game Diagrams* [14]. I include three examples here. All you have to do is count the blocks. The West Wall bottom left block is "variable," optionally included when counting.

Figure 2: Famous irrationals on the walls and floor of the King's Chamber

This is just the first example I was shown, which taught me to pay much closer attention the "weird" ideas that were being put in my head. It was perhaps my "moment of enlightenment."

The main vertical patterns are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The main vertical patterns

The blocks on the KC walls are actually an arrangement of the following digits, where each digit is one row on one wall, except for the bold digits, which are the sum of two rows.

1 1 2 3 3 4 5 5 5 6 7 8 9 **9 9**, and 1 7 **15**.

It will look more familiar once correctly arranged, as

3 1 4 1 5 9 2 6 5 3 5 8 **9 7 9**, and **15 7 1**, which is read as $1.571 \approx \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Figure 4: π and $\pi/2$ on the walls of the King's Chamber

That is π correct to 14 decimals, only one decimal less than what NASA uses [15].

See the cited papers for many more examples.

At the same time, they covered their bases by also doing $\sqrt{10\pi}$ in fractional notation, by treating the number of blocks in each row as the denominator in a unit fraction. The only special case is the double row on the north wall, where the big block is used as an indicator to combine the two rows. (Or, the big block is 1 and the rest is 10.)

Figure 5: Rows are unit fractions

These fractions add up to $5\frac{305}{504}$, which is 5.605 to three decimals. $5.605^2 = 31.416$ to three places. ($\sqrt{10\pi}$ on Khufu's King's Chamber Walls [16])

It may even be possible to read that number from the wall blocks, with the large block again acting as a function indicator.

Figure 6: Possible reading of $5 \frac{305}{504}$

I did not make the rules for the Chamber Game, but just tried to understand how the designers thought as best I could.

There is even a subtle twist with 305 and 504. If you include the 4 with the 305 instead of the 504, then $\frac{309}{500}$ is 0.618, the inverse of the golden ratio. One could use the entrance space for the extra zero. Giza maths humour.

When you consider the level of intelligence and mathematical knowledge required to design the walls of the King's Chamber, so that these and other patterns all work at the same time, you will never look at Giza the same way again. For my part, I wonder if it could have been done without a computer. Changing the number of blocks in even one row will break the patterns.

Giza is a series of layered revelations, where the designers made few assumptions about the people that would be exploring it. So for example, we will find π at 3.14 to two decimals, 3.142 to three decimals, 3.1416 (most favoured) to four decimals, 3.14159 to five decimals, $\sqrt[4]{\frac{2143}{22}}$, and even the 14 decimals as shown.

Table 1: Layered revelations

2.2 The decimal cubit

The dynastic Egyptians used a cubit divided into 28 digits. The exact length of the cubit is still much debated. I have written some texts on the topic, and have come to the conclusion that the original value was 0.5236 metres, or extremely close to that. This is the rounded value of a length of π metres divided by 6, or a length of φ^2 metres divided by 5. See for example *The Beautiful System* [17]. What the metre, or something very close to it, is doing here, is another of the mysteries of Giza, but various things do make sense when considered in metres rather than cubits.

Figure 7: The King's Chamber floor: A simple example of reading things in metres.

The difference in height between Khufu and Khafre is 6 cubits, which is π metres.

An early paper (*The Beautiful Cubit System* [18]) explored the 28 digit cubit, but subsequent research has convinced me that whoever built Giza used a decimal cubit divided into 100 centicubits and 1000 millicubits. This provides a very accurate way to measure, since each division is about half a millimetre.

Petrie (*The Pyramids and Temples of Gizeh*, §141 [19]) had trouble getting 28 digits to add up to one cubit, and instead found evidence (§139) that the builders used a decimal cubit. Petrie is a little vague here, it looks like he is suggesting a cubit divided into 10 rather than 28. Figure 8 shows a comparison between metric and cubits. (All graduations are present in Tikz original, but some get lost between making the PDF and printing. I have tried using SVG and an image, neither produces better results.)

Figure 8: Centimetres and millimetres compared to decimal centicubit and millicubit divisions.

2.3 The speed of light in metres and cubits per second

The speed of light (in a vacuum) is currently defined as 299 792 458 m/s. For the purposes of this discussion, we can also write that as 299.792458 Mm/s.

We can convert to cubits by dividing by 0.5236, giving 572.5600802 M \mathcal{C} /s. An approximation of 572.56 is both short and highly accurate, compared to an equivalent length (299.79) in Mm/s. The cubit version error is 42 m/s, while the metre version error is 2458 m/s.

However, the issue of the speed of light is not so straight-forward. The speed is in metres per second, and the duration of the second has changed over the millennia.

A second as measured by humans is $\frac{\text{length of day}}{\text{seconds in day}}$, or $\frac{\text{length of day}}{86400}$.

The Earth's rate of rotation is slowing down:

“The long-term average rate of change in length of day derived from the time derivative of equation (4.1) is $+1.78 \pm 0.03$ milliseconds per century” (*Measurement of the Earth's rotation: 720 BC to AD 2015* [20])

1.78 milliseconds per century is not much, but a lot depends on how far back we assume Giza was built. The currently accepted date for Khafre's construction is around 2558 BCE, which is 47 to 48 centuries ago. The day would have been 0.084 current seconds shorter, assuming the research is correct, and that the rate is constant. It is probably not constant due to planetary motions in the shorter term, and the Milankovitch cycles in the longer term, but I will assume it is constant for discussion purposes here.

If my correlation with the Big Dipper star map is correct, then Giza was built around 55.5k BCE, or around 575 centuries ago, when the day would have been 1.02 of our current seconds shorter.

Since the “second” at that time will then be shorter, light could not travel so far in one of those “seconds”.

We can compute how far light could travel in $1/86400$ of those days, using the following values:

c 299 792 458 metres/second

delta 0.00178 seconds/century

day 86400 seconds

Item	2558 BCE	55 500 BCE
Centuries ago	47.5	575
Day shorter by (current seconds)	0.08455	1.0235
Length of day (current seconds)	86399.91545	86398.9765
Relative length of second to current	0.999999021412037	0.999988153935185
Difference from 1 current second	9.78587962996436 E-07	1.18460648147467 E-05
Distance light travels in that time (m)	293.3732908	3551.36088844
Speed in that century (m/s)	299792164.6267	299788906.6391
Speed in that century (G/s)	572559519.9135	572553297.6301
Speed in that century (MG/s)	572.5595199	572.5532976

Table 2: The effect of the previously faster Earth rotation on “c”

In 2558 BCE, the speed of light would have been measured as 299 792 164.627 m/s, and 299 788 906.639 m/s in 55.5k BCE. That translates to 572.55952 MG/s and 572.55330 MG/s respectively, compared to the current speed of 572.5600802 MG/s.

I raise this point because the calculation with Khufu shown in §2.4 produces a value of 572.55, which is 572.5533 rounded to two decimals.

The speed of light is difficult to measure. Figure 9 shows the final results from Essen and Gordon-Smith (1946) [21] (see next table), showing that their value is an average from four tests, after picking the best set-up. These are also in km/s, not m/s.

date	mode of resonance	correction factor (1 + 1/2Q)	constant r	measured frequency f'_{imn} (Mcy./sec.)	v_0 (km./sec.)
2. x. 46	E_{010}	1.000028	2.404825	3101.25	299,793
2. x. 46	E_{011}	1.000035	2.404825	3563.80	299,791
25. x. 46	E_{010}	1.000028	2.404825	3101.28	299,796
25. x. 46	E_{011}	1.000035	2.404825	3563.77	299,789

mean value of velocity 299,792 km./sec.

Figure 9: Essen and Gordon-Smith final results

We have no idea, if Giza was indeed intended to provide a reference to *c* in addition to other requirements in the site plan, what the target value was. Wikipedia [22] conveniently lists some historical values, as in Table 3. I've added Giza, calculated from the Khufu circles method, and corrected some figures [23]. The accuracy is relative to the current value and length of the second.

Year	Who, method	Value km/s	% Accuracy
2550 / 55.5k BCE	Giza (official date / my date)	299 787.3459	99.998295
1675	Rømer and Huygens, moons of Jupiter	220 000	73.384101
1729	James Bradley, aberration of light	301 000	99.597207
1849	Hippolyte Fizeau, toothed wheel	315 000	94.927310
1862	Léon Foucault, rotating mirror	298 000 ± 500	99.402100
1907	Rosa and Dorsey, EM constants	299 788 ± 30	99.998513
1926	Albert A. Michelson, rotating mirror	299 796 ± 4	99.998819
1946	Essen and Gordon-Smith, cavity resonator	299 792	99.999847
1958	K.D. Froome, radio interferometry	299 792.50 ± 0.10	99.999986
1972	Evenson et al., laser interferometry	299 792.457 ± 0.0011	99.999999
1983	17th CGPM, definition of the metre	299 792.458 (as defined)	100.000000

Table 3: Historical values for *c*

2.4 Giza, c and α

Assorted mathematical and scientific constants are found all over Giza. These are discussed frequently by various authors as well as in my previous papers, which you can find via my ORCID shown in the title block on page 1.

Two of the most puzzling of these constants are the speed of light, and the inverse of the fine-structure constant.

Alternative Giza researchers are typically familiar with the ways that the Great Pyramid encodes the speed of light, the most common method is shown in Figure 10. I discuss this method at length in *G1, c and G: Khufu's pyramid, the speed of light, and the royal cubit, compared* [24], and discuss other methods in *Another reference to the speed of light by the Great Pyramid* [25].

Figure 10: The circumcircle and incircle for Khufu

The red contained incircle has a diameter of 440 G , while the blue surrounding circumcircle has a diameter of $440\sqrt{2} \text{ G}$. The difference between their circumferences, using π at 3.1416 and $\sqrt{2}$ at 1.4142, is 572.55 G , representing the speed of light in MG/s .

I need to briefly discuss the Fine-structure constant. The mathematics and science here are just for background, the important things are the number 137, and that it is important.

The Fine-structure constant is a fundamental physical constant which quantifies the strength of the electromagnetic interaction between elementary charged particles. It dates from around 1916, and is a dimensionless number, usually represented by alpha (α), with a value of about 0.007297352569.

Since that string of decimals is unpleasant to work with, physicists often use the inverse, 137.035999, approximated to 137.

The Fine-structure Constant is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{e^2}{2\epsilon_0 hc}$$

where

- e is the elementary charge ($1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$)
- ϵ_0 is the electric constant ($8.8541878128(13) \times 10^{-12} \text{ F}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$)
- h is the Planck constant ($6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1}$)
- c is the speed of light ($299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)

The formula contains some of the most fundamental and important physical constants, including the speed of light. The units all cancel each other out, leaving us with a dimensionless number.

Interestingly, if we take the square root of $\frac{c}{\alpha}$, with c at 572.55 MG/s , and α rounded to their usual 4 decimals, i.e. $\sqrt{\frac{572.55}{0.0073}}$, you get 280.06, or 280 rounded, the height of the great pyramid. So the Great Pyramid's base gives us c as shown above, and its height gives us c with α .

Alpha even pops up in the ratio between the volumes of Khafre and Khufu.

$$\left(\frac{Volume_{Khafre}}{Volume_{Khufu}}\right)^2 \approx 0.73 = 100 \times 0.0073 \approx 100\alpha$$

“When I die my first question to the Devil will be: What is the meaning of the fine-structure constant?”

Wolfgang Pauli

“It has been a mystery ever since it was discovered more than fifty years ago, and all good theoretical physicists put this number up on their wall and worry about it.”

Richard P. Feynman

The points here are that 137 is a very important number to physicists, and the frequent appearance of 137 at Giza is an unsolved puzzle.

3 Khafre and c

Khafre's accepted dimensions are a square base of 411 cG, with a height of 274 cG. We can rewrite that as 3 × 137 by 2 × 137, or, switching to cG, 3 × 13700 by 2 × 13700. The side view is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Khafre dimensions in cG

We can read the formula for the speed of light directly from the numbers in the diagram, as

$$c \approx 13700^{\frac{2}{3}} \approx 572.55$$

Alternatively, $c \approx \sqrt[3]{13700^2}$ or $c \approx (\sqrt[3]{13700})^2$.

In terms of Khafre's dimensions in cubits, it is

$$c \approx ((\text{base} - \text{height}) \times 100)^{\frac{\text{height}}{\text{base}}} = ((411 - 274) \times 100)^{\frac{274}{411}} = 13700^{\frac{274}{411}} \approx 572.55$$

In terms of Khafre's dimensions in centicubits, it is

$$c \approx (\text{base_cG} - \text{height_cG})^{\frac{\text{height_cG}}{\text{base_cG}}} = (41100 - 27400)^{\frac{27400}{41100}} = 13700^{\frac{27400}{41100}} \approx 572.55$$

This is arguably one of the most amazing formulas hidden at Giza.

The value 572.55, read as M/s for the speed of light, is the same value (to two decimals) as that given by the Khufu circles method.

The answer with more decimals is 572.5503855, which we can compare to the current and historically adjusted values calculated previously.

Year	Value	Delta M€/s	Delta m/s	% Accuracy
2024 CE	572.5600802	0.0096947	5076.1378	99.9983068
2558 BCE	572.5595397	0.0091542	4793.1407	99.9984012
55500 BCE	572.5532976	0.0029093	1523.2946	99.9994919

Table 4: Comparing the answer to current and historical values for c

The answer aligns best with the speed of light as it would have been calculated in 55.5k BCE. The accuracy is obviously affected by pyramids having whole-cubit dimensions.

4 Conclusion

The Khufu and Khafre pyramids have stood next to each other for millennia. Khufu is based on the Kepler triangle, rounded to whole-cubit dimensions, and Khafre on the classic Pythagorean 3-4-5 triangle. These two triangles are unique, with Kepler having the sides in geometric sequence, and Pythagoras in arithmetic sequence.

It is curious that these two pyramids, with different design paradigms, should both have been built with dimensions that lead easily to the same number, 572.55, which can be read as a good approximation for the speed of light in millions of cubits per second.

The calculations used *only* work with a base of 440 for Khufu, and base of 411 for Khafre, with its height dictated by the Pythagorean design.

The conventional view is that these are mere co-incidences, because claiming that the 4th dynasty had knowledge of the speed of light (or π , φ , or e , for that matter, all present at Giza) leads to logical contradictions.

“Contradictions do not exist. Whenever you think that you are facing a contradiction, check your premises. You will find that one of them is wrong.”

Ayn Rand

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